

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

“SYNTHESIS, MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES AND SCREENING OF ANTICONVULSANT ACTIVITY OF NOVEL PYRROLYL PYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES”

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 21/04/2023

Available online

01/06/2023

Keywords

Anticonvulsant,
Pyrrole,
Pyrimidine,
Acetyl Choline Esterase-II
Inhibitors.

ABSTRACT

The novel series of pyrrolyl pyrimidine derivatives were synthesized and molecular docking studies were carried out further few compounds evaluated for anticonvulsant activity against MES and PTZ induced convulsions. Purity of the newly synthesized compounds confirmed by using TLC and structures were confirmed by using IR, NMR, ¹³C and Mass spectra. In present work 4-Pyrrole-1-yl acetophenone (1) is refluxed with appropriate benzaldehyde (2) in 40% NaOH for 3 h to form substituted chalcone derivatives (3a-j) which is further stirred with urea in ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution for 3 hr to form titled compounds (4-(1H pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl (2-hydroxy-6- substituted phenyl) 1, 2 dihydro pyrimidine-5yl) methanone (4a-j). Docking study was performed by Surfex-Dock program that is interfaced with Sybyl-X 2.0. Compounds 4m and 4n showed excellent consensus score at 7.21 & 5.92 respectively. Docking study reveals that all the compounds have showed very good docking score against the enzyme. The few newly synthesized compounds were screened for their anticonvulsant activity. Compounds 4d (13.49±0.80) and compound 4e (9.64±0.48) showed significantly decrease in hind limb extension against MES induced convulsions. Compound 4b (136.5 ± 2.04) and 4e (126.7 ± 2.29) showed protection against PTZ induced convulsions. Simultaneously activity is compared with control and standard group. The newly synthesized novel series of pyrrolyl pyrimidine derivatives may be developed into potential class of anticonvulsant agents in future.

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Please cite this article in press as **Channabasappa S. Hallikeri.** et al. “Synthesis, Molecular Docking Studies and Screening of Anticonvulsant Activity of Novel Pyrrolyl Pyrimidine Derivatives”. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2023:13(05).

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INTRODUCTION

Epilepsy is a neurological disorder that affects a wide range of people throughout the world [1]. Epilepsy has now become the most serious brain disorder, which accounts for about 1% of the world's effected with these diseases. Epilepsy is a neurological disorder characterized by excessive electrical discharge in brain, which cause seizures. The therapeutic strategy in countering epilepsy involves reducing neuronal excitability through different mechanistic pathways.

In many tropical countries the occurrence of epilepsy was estimated to be greater than 0.5% of a given population and is higher in male than female with a majority having their first attack before the age of twenty [2]. A number of synthetic antiepileptic drugs are available in practice; however, their effectiveness does not hold true with the entire range of population suffering from this disorder. The conventional antiepileptic agents like phenytoin and sodium valporate associated with them several serious side effects in particularly neurotoxicity.

It has been observed that the presently obtainable antiepileptic drugs are unable to control seizures effectively in as many as 25% of the patients. As majority of antiepileptic drugs are consumed life long, collateral administration of other drugs predisposes to the risk of drug interaction. The current therapeutic treatment of epilepsy with modern antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) is associated with side-effects, dose-related and chronic toxicity, and teratogenic effects, and approximately 30% of the patients continue to have seizures with current AEDs therapy. The currently available synthetic antiepileptic drugs provide seizure control in upto 70% patient with epilepsy, the remaining patient have stubborn epilepsy.

Thus, there is still need to develop new drugs with greater clinical efficacy, bearable minimum side effect, devoid of undesirable drug interactions and better pharmacokinetic properties [2, 3].

Pyrrole is one of the most omnipresent heterocycles in the plant and animal kingdom because of its occurrence as a subunit of chlorophyll, haem and some bile pigments. Biosynthetically related vitamin B₁₂ is a tetrapyrrole. A various number of antibiotics are also derivatives of pyrrole. The indole ring system, in which pyrrole is fused with a benzene ring, is widespread in nature and it is also present in the tryptophan, serotonin, many alkaloids and indigo [4]. Pyrrole and its derivatives have shown to possess biological activities such as antibacterial [5], analgesics [6], antitubercular [7, 8], inflammatory, anticonvulsant [9] and antiallergic [10] Several macromolecular antibiotics having pyrrole structure were isolated from biological sources and their activities were defined.

Considering the above factors, it is suitable to mention here that a drug, which can effectively treat the convulsions within a short duration of time, is most advisable and advancement in this area is the need of the hour.

Experimental

Melting points were determined using the Shital-digital programmable melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Bruker FTIR spectrophotometer. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE II at 400 and 100 MHz, respectively; chemical shifts are expressed in parts per million (ppm) relative to TMS. The abbreviations used to describe the peak patterns are: (b) broad, (s) singlet, (d) doublet, (t) triplet, (q) quartet, and (m) multiplate. Mass spectra (MS) were recorded in a JEOL GCMATE II GC-Mass spectrometer and Shimadzu QP 20105 GC-Mass spectrometer. Analytical thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on precoated TLC sheets of silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) visualized by long- and short- wavelength ultraviolet (UV) lamps.

SCHEME-I

Synthesis of 1-(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)ethen-1-one (1):

2,5-dimethoxy tetrahydrofuran (16 g, 0.12 mol) was added to para-amino acetophenone (13.52 g, 0.1 mol) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) and reaction mixture were heated to reflux for 30 mins. The reaction mixture was poured on to ice cold water, precipitated solid was filtered and dried. Solid crude product was recrystallized from ethanol and obtained as brown crystals. Melting point- 118 – 120°C.

Synthesis of (E)-1-(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)-3-substituted phenylprop-2-en-1-one. (3a-j):

A solution of sodium hydroxide (40%) in water and rectified spirit was placed in a flask provided with mechanical stirrer. The flask was immersed in a bath of crushed ice. 1-(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)ethen-1-one (0.99 g, 0.005 mol) was added with constant stirring then appropriate benzaldehydes (0.053 g, 0.005 mol) was added to the solution. The temperature of mixture was kept at about 25 °C and stirred vigorously until the mixture was thick enough to retard stirring (4h). Stirrer was removed and the mixture was kept at 8 °C overnight. The product was filtered with suction on a Buchner funnel, washed with cold water until the washings were neutral to litmus and further washed with ice cold ethanol. The crude product was recrystallized from ethanol.

Synthesis of (4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl (2-hydroxy-6-substituted phenyl) 1, 2 dihydro pyrimidine-5-yl) methanone. (4a-j):

In a mixture of appropriate chalcones (3a-j) (2.5g, 10mmol) and different nucleophilic reagents namely urea (0.06g, 10mmol) was dissolved in ethanol sodium hydroxide (4g, NaOH and 10ml, ethanol) solution and reaction mixture were stirred for about 2-3h with magnetic stirrer. Then mixture was poured in to 400ml cold water with continuous stirring for 1h and reaction mixture were kept overnight in a refrigerator, precipitate obtained was filtered, washed and recrystallized from ethanol. The purity of the compound was confirmed by melting point and TLC.

The purity of the all newly synthesized compounds were confirmed by melting point and TLC. The structures of newly synthesized compound were confirmed by analytical and spectral data such as IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectra.

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl) (6-(2-chlorophenyl)-2-hydroxy-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4a)

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm⁻¹: 3386.01(NH), 3136.64 (OH), 2921.88 (CH Ar), 1650.18 (C=N), 1600.10(C=O), 1519.20(C-N), 1251.69 (C=C).; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400MHz, δ): 1.4(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.16 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.28-6.4(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.06-7.26(m, 4H phenyl C₄, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.33-7.38 (d, 2H phenyl C₂, C₅-H), 7.5-7.7 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H); MS (EI): m/z = found 362.00[M⁺]; calcd. 361.38.

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (6-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-hydroxy-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4b):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3421.61(NH), 3141.74 (OH), 2922.78 (CH Ar), 1652.18 (C=N), 1599.38(C=O), 1332.05(C-N), 1224.90 (C=C); ^1H NMR(CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.25(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.26 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.22-6.33(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.16-7.26(m, 4H phenyl C₄, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.40-7.44 (d, 2H phenyl C₂, C₅-H), 8.02-8.25 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (6-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-hydroxy-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4c):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3435.40(NH), 3141.38 (OH), 2934.88 (CH Ar), 1656.18 (C=N), 1598.67(C=O), 1446.39(C-N), 1250.28 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.42(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.26 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.22-6.33(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.21-7.23(m, 3H phenyl C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.40-7.44 (d, 2H phenyl C₂, C₅-H), 7.70-7.85 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (2-hydroxy-6-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4d):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3423.50(NH), 3130.61 (OH), 2921.34 (CH Ar), 1653.70 (C=N), 1599.35(C=O), 1335.04(C-N), 1269.04 (C=C); ^1H NMR(CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.45(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.20 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.20-6.28(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.21-7.23(m, 4H phenyl C₄, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.40-7.44 (d, 2H phenyl C₂, C₅-H), 7.70-8.22 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 9.48 (s, 1H, -OH, phenyl C₄-H); MS (EI): m/z = found 360.00[M⁺]; calcd. 359.39

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (2-hydroxy-6-(3-methoxyphenyl)-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4e):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3427.50(NH), 3070.61 (OH), 2923.84 (CH Ar), 1653.70 (C=N), 1598.70(C=N), 1258.35(C=O), 1269.04 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.46(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 3.93 (s, 3H, OCH₃, phenyl C₃-H) 4.23 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.23-6.28(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.26-7.29(m, 4H phenyl C₄, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.43-7.48 (d, 2H phenyl C₂, C₅-H), 7.78-8.30 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (6-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-hydroxy-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4f):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3383.01(NH), 3139.62 (OH), 2922.90 (CH Ar), 1656.18 (C=N), 1596.10(C=O), 1520.26(C-N), 1251.46 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.46(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.12 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.30-6.42(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.16-7.36(m, 4H phenyl C₄, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.43-7.68 (d, 2H phenyl C₂, C₅-H), 7.82-8.02 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H); MS (EI): m/z = found 379.00[M⁺]; calcd. 377.83

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (6-(2-fluorophenyl)-2-hydroxy-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4g):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3426.63(NH), 3151.54 (OH), 3004.28 (CH Ar), 1662.28 (C=N), 1586.32(C=O), 1442.11(C-N), 1224.92 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.32(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.36 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.12-6.36(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.16-7.26(m, 4H phenyl C₄, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.40-7.44 (d, 2H phenyl C₃, C₅-H), 8.02-8.25 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (2-hydroxy-6-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4h):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3523.56(NH), 3129.43 (OH), 2926.38 (CH Ar), 1683.80 (C=N), 1600.22(C=O), 1334.04(C-N), 1279.04 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.26(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.28 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.26-6.38(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.28-7.33(m, 4H phenyl C₄, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.36-7.44 (d, 2H phenyl C₃, C₅-H), 7.78-8.12 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 9.33 (s, 1H, -OH, phenyl C₂-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (2-hydroxy-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4i):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3429.65(NH), 3045.41 (OH), 2922.54 (CH Ar), 1666.70 (C=N), 1602.30(C=N), 1265.32(C=O), 1339.31 (C=C) 1165.24 (C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.37(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.01 (s, 3H, OCH₃, phenyl C₄-H) 4.63 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.23-6.36(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.24-7.49(m, 4H phenyl C₃, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.43-7.48 (d, 2H phenyl C₂, C₅-H), 7.78-8.30 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl) phenyl) (6-(4-bromophenyl)-2-hydroxy-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl) methanone (4j):

IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3521.66(NH), 3242.54 (OH), 2942.72 (CH Ar), 1666.20 (C=N), 1579.78(C=O), 1331.35(C-N), 1226.50 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400MHz, δ): 1.37(s, 1H, pyrimidine, NH), 4.66 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.27-6.43(d, 2H, pyrrole C₃, C₄-H), 7.26-7.34(m, 4H phenyl C₄, C₆-H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H), 7.56-7.77 (d, 2H phenyl C₂, C₅-H), 8.12-8.36 (m, 4H, bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

Molecular docking

Molecular docking was used to clarify the binding mode of the compounds to provide straight forward information for further structural optimization.

It is reported that the anticonvulsant, antiepileptic and antiseizure drugs may account for hCA inhibition. The choice of consistent hCA enzyme was based on reported literature. Hence, X-ray coordinates of the hCA II isomer was taken from the RCSB data bank (PDB file with code 3F8E), in which, cis-2-hydroxy-4-(1S-3-methylbutyl)-3-methoxy-cinamic acid perfectly fits with the active site.

X-ray coordinates of the hCA II isomer was taken from the RCSB data bank (PDB file with code 3F8E), in which, cis-2-hydroxy-4-(1S-3-methylbutyl)-3-methoxy-cinamic acid perfectly fits with the active site was extracted from the Brookhaven Protein Database (PDB <http://www.rcsb.org/pdb>). The proteins were prepared for docking by adding polar hydrogen atom with Gasteiger-Huckel charges and water molecules were removed. The 3D structure of the ligands was generated by the SKETCH module implemented in the SYBYL program (Tripos Inc., St. Louis, USA) and its energy-minimized conformation was obtained with the help of the Tripos force field using Gasteiger-Huckel charges and molecular docking was performed with Surflex-Dock program that is interfaced with Sybyl-X 2.0. and other miscellaneous parameters were assigned with the default values given by the software.

Pharmacological activity

1) *In vivo* evaluation of anticonvulsant activity.

a) Maximal electroshock (MES) induced convulsion in rats [11]:

The anticonvulsant property of the drug in this model was assessed by its ability to protect against MES induced convulsions. The animals are first weigh and are select for the experiment depending on weight. The rats are then divided into different groups of six rats in each. Control group will receive saline, standard group receive 25 mg/kg of phenytoin, other groups receive therapeutic dose of testing drugs respectively.

Maximal electroshock (Inco Electro convulsimeter) of 150 mA current for 0.2 seconds will be administered through ear electrode to induce convulsions in the control and drug treated animals. The severity of convulsions will be assessed by duration of tonic flexion, tonic extensor, clonus, stupor and recovery phase for each animal. The duration of each phase for each animal (in sec) will be measured by using stopwatch.

b) Pentylene tetrazole (PTZ) induced Convulsion in rats [12]:

The anti-convulsant property of the drug in this model will be assessed by its ability to delay the onset of action and protection against PTZ induced convulsions.

Healthy albino Wister rats of either sex is used. The rats will be divided into different groups of six rats in each group. Control group receive saline; standard group receive 4mg/kg body weight of diazepam and other groups receive therapeutic dose of testing drugs respectively. Pentylentetrazole (80mg/kg body weight) will be administered intraperitoneally to induce convulsions in the animals of all groups 45 min to 1 hr after administration of saline, standard drug and testing drugs.

The data will be expressed as mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey multiple comparison test will be carried out with Graph Pad Prism software (version 3.0). Differences between means were considered significant at $p < 0.01$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthetic and spectral study

The synthetic scheme employed for preparation of the title compounds is depicted in scheme I.

In this work 4-Pyrrole-1-yl acetophenone (1) is refluxed with appropriate benzaldehyde (2) in 40% NaOH for 3 h to form substituted chalcone derivatives (3a-j) which is further stirred with urea in ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution for 3 hr to form titled compounds (4-(1H pyrrol-1yl) phenyl (2-hydroxy-6- substituted phenyl) 1, 2 dihydro pyrimidine-5yl) methanone.(4a-j). All the newly synthesized compounds were purified by passing through column chromatography. The purity of the compounds was confirmed by melting point and TLC. The structure of newly synthesized compound was established on the basis of analytical and spectral data.

The IR spectrum of 4a exhibited bands at 3386.01 cm^{-1} , 3136.64 cm^{-1} which were due to (-NH), (-OH) stretching frequencies respectively. The (C-H aromatic) absorption band displayed at 2921.88 cm^{-1} , (C=N), (C=O), (C-N) and (C=C) absorption band displayed at 1652 cm^{-1} , 1599 cm^{-1} , 1332 cm^{-1} and 1224 cm^{-1} respectively. In the ^1H NMR spectrum of 4a showed singlet at δ 1.25 due to protons of (pyrimidine NH), singlets at δ 4.26 due to one proton of -OH, doublet at δ value 6.33 due to two protons of pyrrole-C₃ and C₄, multiplet value 7.16 to 7.26 for two protons of phenyl-C₄ and C₆ two protons of pyrrole C₂ and C₅, doublet at δ value 7.44 due to two protons of phenyl- C₂ and C₅, multiplet at δ value 8.02 to 8.25 due to four protons of bridging phenyl C₂, C₃, C₅ and C₆. MS (EI): m/z = found 362.00[M⁺]; calculated. 361.38.

Docking study of pyrrolyl pyrimidine derivatives (Scheme-I):

To investigate the mechanism of anti-convulsant activity and detailed intermolecular interactions between the synthesized compounds, molecular docking studies were performed on the hCA II isomer which was taken from the RCSB data bank (PDB file with code 3F8E) using the surflex-dock programme of sybyl-X 2.0 software. All the inhibitors along with the ligand were docked into the active site of ENR as shown in Fig. 1A and B. The predicted binding energies of the compounds are listed in **Table 1**. The docking study revealed that all the compounds have showed very good docking score against the enzyme.

As depicted in the **fig. 1(A-C)**, compound **4b** makes three hydrogen bonding interactions at the active site of the enzyme (PDB ID: 3F8E), among those an interaction was of oxygen atom of carbonyl group of pyrimidine5-methenone with hydrogen atom of THR200 (C=O-----H-THR200, 1.96 Å), oxygen atom of hydroxyl group present on the 2nd position of pyrimidine ring makes hydrogen bond with hydrogen atom of THR199 (HO-----H-THR199, 1.99 Å) and remaining another hydrogen bonding interaction raised from the hydrogen atom of hydroxyl group present on the 2nd position of pyrimidine ring with oxygen atom of THR199 (OH----O-THR199, 1.83 Å).

As depicted in **fig. 3(A-C)**, compound **4j** makes three hydrogen bonding interactions at the active site of the enzyme (PDB ID: 3F8E), among those an interaction was of oxygen atom of carbonyl group of pyrimidine5-methenone with hydrogen atom of THR200 (C=O-----H-THR200, 1.93 Å), oxygen atom of hydroxyl group present on the 2nd position of pyrimidine ring makes hydrogen bond with hydrogen atom of THR199 (HO-----H-THR199, 1.95 Å) and remaining another hydrogen bonding interaction raised from the hydrogen atom of hydroxyl group present on the 2nd position of pyrimidine ring with oxygen atom of THR199 (OH----O-THR199, 1.83 Å).

The binding interaction of 3F8E_ligand with enzyme active sites shows four bonding interactions and the docked view of the same has been depicted in **Fig. 4(A-C)**.

Figure5 (A&B) represents the hydrophobic and hydrophilic amino acids surrounded to the studied compound **4b & 4j**.

All the compounds showed consensus score in the range 7.21-3.08, indicating the summary of all forces of interaction between ligands and the enzyme and also, we saw that the studied compounds have showed same type of interaction with amino acid residue (THR199) as that of reference 3F8E_ligand. This indicates that molecules preferentially bind to enzyme in comparison to the reference 3F8E_ligand (Table 01).

Table 1. Surflex Docking score (kcal/mol) of the pyrrolyl pyrimidines.

Compounds	C Score ^a	Crash Score ^b	Polar Score ^c	D Score ^d	PMF Score ^e	G Score ^f	Chem Score ^g
3F8E_ligand	7.54	-0.50	4.80	-103.838	-61.785	-135.025	-23.851
4m	7.21	-2.69	3.17	-142.206	-79.678	-237.307	-31.5
4n	5.92	-3.15	4.26	-143.954	-79.881	-187.630	-33.308
4e	5.89	-3.02	3.28	-145.290	-89.403	-214.804	-33.980
4d	5.65	-2.43	3.20	-126.160	-79.561	-171.581	-27.600
4p	5.31	-2.44	3.06	-131.790	-79.858	-204.315	-31.371
4i	5.16	-1.91	2.13	-130.789	-58.940	-165.582	-25.603
4b	5.12	-3.28	3.00	-133.283	-78.503	-185.730	-29.290
4h	4.62	-2.95	2.90	-130.256	-83.961	-194.312	-28.863
4g	4.62	-2.95	2.90	-130.256	-83.961	-194.312	-28.863
4j	4.18	-2.37	3.31	-118.932	-65.070	-169.862	-26.256
4l	3.57	-1.53	2.30	-136.917	-72.920	-149.416	-23.613
4f	3.47	-1.36	2.29	-137.846	-67.649	-158.523	-22.498
4c	3.31	-1.02	0.14	-103.538	-67.695	-146.805	-21.678
4o	3.18	-2.26	1.94	-130.290	-58.814	-161.702	-24.454
4a	5.31	-2.44	3.06	-131.790	-79.858	-204.315	-31.371

^a C Score (Consensus Score) integrates a number of popular scoring functions for ranking the affinity of ligands bound to the active site of a receptor and reports the output of total score.

^b Crash-score revealing the inappropriate penetration into the binding site. Crash scores close to 0 are favorable. Negative numbers indicate penetration.

^c Polar indicating the contribution of the polar interactions to the total score. The polar score may be useful for excluding docking results that make no hydrogen bonds.

^d D-score for charge and van der Waals interactions between the protein and the ligand.

^e PMF-score indicating the Helmholtz free energies of interactions for protein-ligand atom pairs (Potential of Mean Force, PMF).

^f G-score showing hydrogen bonding, complex (ligand-protein), and internal (ligand-ligand) energies.

^g Chem-score points for H-bonding, lipophilic contact, and rotational entropy, along with an intercept term.

Figure 1. Docked view of all the compounds at the active site of the enzyme PDB ID: 3F8E.

Figure 2. Docked view of compound 4b at the active site of the enzyme PDB: 3F8E.

Figure 3. Docked view of compound 4j at the active site of the enzyme PDB: 3F8E.

Figure 4. Docked view of Ligand at the active site of the enzyme PDB: 3F8E.

Figure 5. A) Hydrophobic amino acids surrounded to compounds 4b (green colour) and 4j (cyan colour). B) Hydrophilic amino acids surrounded to compounds 4b and 4j.

Pharmacological Screening

Anticonvulsant activity of Pyrrolyl pyrimidine derivatives

The models used to evaluate the effectiveness of few synthesized compounds were selected on basis of molecular docking studies compounds 4b, 4d, 4e and 4i are (1) Maximal Electroshock Seizure and (2) Pentalene tetrazole seizure.

The MES model is generally used to evaluate the anticonvulsant drugs against generalized tonic-clonic seizure (grand mal) in rodents, which is related to intensity of current stimulus and the dose. MES produced various phases of convulsion i.e. Flexion, Extension, Clonus and Stupor. The duration of tonic extension of the hind limb was used as end point i.e. prevention or decrease in the duration of hind limb extension was considered as a protective action.

Table-No 2: Evaluation of anticonvulsant activity of different pyrrolyl pyrimidine derivatives against MES induced convulsions.

Group	Treatment (mg/kg b.w.)	Time (sec) in Various Phases of Convulsions (Mean±SEM)				Recovery/ Death
		Flexon	Extensor	Clonus	Stupor	
1.	Control (Saline 1ml/rat)	2.81±0.025	23.50±0.71	3.26±0.12	219.6±4.3	Recovery
2.	Standard Phenytoin (25)	0.036±0.012***	0.00±0.00***	0.00±0.00***	5.04±0.38***	Recovery
3.	Compound 4b (10)	1.84±0.12	15.64±0.85***	1.66±0.15***	158.2±6.30***	Recovery
4.	Compound 4d (10)	2.59±0.33	13.49±0.80***	1.74±0.10***	165.8±7.21***	Recovery
5.	Compound 4e (10)	1.27±0.36***	9.64±0.48***	1.03±0.06***	134.5±5.73***	Recovery

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 compared with the respective Control.

The synthesized compounds 4b, 4d, 4e and 4i were given orally with the help of stomach tube to rats. The results of tested compounds are compared with the result produced by control. The data resulted from anticonvulsant effect of different tested compounds showed that compounds 4b, 4d, 4e and 4i decrease the duration of hind limb extension, compound 4b (15.64±0.85sec), compound 4d (13.49±0.80sec), compound 4e (9.64±0.48sec), and compound 4i (12.58±1.5sec) which are highly significant when compared to control (23.50±0.71sec).

The synthesized compound 4e also showed significantly decrease in durations of Flexion, Clonus and stupor phase. Compounds 4b, 4d and 4i showed decrease in durations of Clonus and stupor.

Table No 3: Evaluation of anticonvulsant activity of different pyrrolyl pyrimidine derivatives against PTZ induced convulsions.

Group	Treatment (mg/kg b.w.) (Dose)	Duration of Convulsions in Seconds (Mean±SEM)	% Of Mortality
1.	Control (Saline 1 ml/kg) + PTZ [80mg]	562.6 ± 2.09	100%
2.	Diazepam + PTZ [4 + 80]	0.00 ± 0.00***	0%
3.	Compound 4b + PTZ [10 + 80]	136.5 ± 2.04***	15%
4.	Compound 4d + PTZ [10 + 80]	315.5 ± 2.37***	50%
5.	Compound 4e+ PTZ [10 + 80]	126.7 ± 2.29***	15%
6.	Compound 4i + PTZ [10 + 80]	263.7 ± 3.82***	35%

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 compared with the respective Control.

The anti-convulsant property of the drug in this model will be assessed by its ability to delay the onset of action and protection against PTZ induced convulsions.

From the statistical data it was observed that compound 4b (136.5 ± 2.04 sec), compound 4d (315.5 ± 2.37 sec), compound 4e (126.7 ± 2.29 sec) and compound 4i (263.7 ± 3.82 sec) showed highly significant anti-convulsant activity against PTZ induced seizures as compared to the effect produced by control (562.6 ± 2.09 sec).

CONCLUSIONS

The title compounds were obtained by 4-Pyrrole-1-yl acetophenone (1) is refluxed with appropriate benzaldehyde (2) in 40% NaOH for 3 h to form substituted chalcone derivatives (3a-j) which is further stirred with urea in ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution for 3 hr to form titled compounds (4-(1H pyrrol-1yl) phenyl (2-hydroxy-6- substituted phenyl) 1, 2 dihydro pyrimidine-5yl) methanone. (4a-j). All the newly synthesized compounds were purified by passing through column chromatography. The purity of the compounds was confirmed by melting point and TLC. The structure of newly synthesized compound was established on the basis of analytical and spectral data. To investigate the mechanism of anti-convulsant activity and detailed intermolecular interactions between the synthesized compounds, molecular docking studies were performed on the hCA II isomer which was taken from the RCSB data bank (PDB file with code 3F8E) using the surflex-dock programme of sybyl-X 2.0 software. The docking study revealed that all the compounds have showed very good docking score against the enzyme. Synthesized compounds **4b**, **4d**, **4e**, and **4i** screened for in-vivo anticonvulsant activity against MES and PTZ induced convulsions and these compounds showed significant anticonvulsant activity when compared with control group against both MES and PTZ induced convulsions, based on docking and screening results, it can be concluded that combination of pyrrole and pyrimidine improve anticonvulsant activity of synthesized compounds. Hence these compounds can consider as a lead molecule for future research. Present work is can recommended for future work.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors immensely thank research support from the Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bangalore, Karnataka (Project Code-19PH259 Ref No: RGU/ADV-RES/BR-19/2019-20 Dated:03.02.2020). We also thank Dr. V.G. Jamakandi, Dean and Dr. H. V. Dambal, President, S. E. T's College of Pharmacy for providing the facilities. We thank Director, SAIF, Panjab University, Chandigarh, Panjab, India provided some of the NMR and mass spectral data.

List of Abbreviations

°C	Degree centigrade
CDCl ₃	Deuterated chloroform
Conc	Concentrated
DMSO	Dimethyl sulphoxide
DMF	Dimethyl formamide
FT-IR	Fourier Transform Infrared
Gm	Gram
hr/h	Hour
M.P.	Melting Point
Min	Minutes
Mol	Mole
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
pH	Hydrogen ion concentration
Ppm	Parts per million
R _f	Retention factor
TLC	Thin Layer Chromatography
TMS	Tetra methyl silane
MIC	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

Authors' agreements

Authors hereby declare that there is no conflict of interest for the publication.

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